

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

DOCUMENTATION OF RISIS DATASETS Cheetah (version 3.0)

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1 Basic characteristics

The Cheetah dataset (version 3.0) contains geographical, industry, accounting and ownership information on ten cohorts of medium-sized firms that experienced turnover or employment fast growth rates in the periods 2008-11, 2009-12, 2010-13, 2011-14, 2012-15, 2013-16, 2014-17, 2015-18, 2016-19 and 2017-20. These fast growing medium-sized firms (FGMFs) are located in 30 European countries (EU27, Norway, Switzerland and the UK). Cheetah covers an overall number of 129,752 firms.

The aim of the Cheetah dataset is to cover the long-term economic performance of FGMFs, as one of the main pillars of the European industrial and technological system.

The legal name of the operating organization is POLITECNICO DI MILANO, Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering, located in VIA LAMBRUSCHINI 4/B, MILANO, 20156, Italy represented by Prof. Raffaella Cagliano, Head of Department (or her authorized representative).

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2 Dataset content

2.1 Definition and description of observations

The Cheetah dataset includes medium-sized firms that experienced fast-growth rates either in terms of three-years employment growth or three-years turnover growth in at least one of the growth periods of 2008-11, 2009-12, 2010-13, 2011-14, 2012-15, 2013-16, 2014-17, 2015-18, 2016-19 and 2017-20, and are located in 30 European countries.

The dataset includes 129,752 FGMFs. The inclusion criteria for a firm to be included in the current version of the Cheetah dataset are as follows:

- firms must be located in Europe (EU27, Norway, Switzerland and the UK);
- firms are medium-sized at the beginning of each observation period (2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017);
- firms experienced fast-growth (either in the number of employees or in turnover) in at least one of the seven observation periods (2008-11; 2009-12; 2010-13; 2011-14; 2012-15; 2013-16; 2014-17; 2015-18; 2016-19; 2017-20).

The Cheetah dataset is composed by three tables:

1. Main Table, which contains information on basic firm characteristics, fast-growth indicators, and accounting information. The unit of observation is the FGMF;
2. Ownership Table, which contains information on the ownership structure (shareholder information) of FGMFs. The main unit of observation is the shareholder-FGMF dyad;
3. M&A Table, which contains information on M&A deals conducted by FGMFs. The main unit of observation is the M&A deal (i.e. the FGMF-target firm-date triad).

2.2 Data acquisition and processing

The main source of information of the Cheetah dataset is Orbis (<https://orbis.bvdinfo.com>). The data collection process consisted in the following main steps:

1. Identification of European medium-sized firms (employee, turnover and balance sheet criteria).
2. Selection of fast growing firms by applying the OECD definition.
3. Data collection and organization of accounting information.
4. Data collection and organization of ownership information.
5. Data collection and organization of information on M&A activity.
6. Geocoding.

In what follows, we describe the data collection process in detail.

2.2.1 Identification of European medium-sized firms

Medium-sized firms are defined according to definitions of EUROSTAT and *Entreprise de taille intermédiaire* (ETI). EUROSTAT defines medium-sized firms as firms with a number of employees between 50 and 249, and either a turnover of not exceeding €50 million or a balance sheet total of not exceeding €43 million. ETIs are firms with a number of employees between 250 and 4999, and either a turnover of not exceeding €1.5 billion or a balance sheet total of not exceeding €2 billion. A firm that has less than 250 employees but a turnover of more than €50 million and a balance sheet total of more than €43 million is also considered a ETI.

In order to identify European medium-sized firms in Orbis we first applied the turnover and balance sheet thresholds. Accordingly, we selected firms (located in the 30 European countries) with a turnover lower than €1,5 billion or a balance sheet total lower than €2 billion at the beginning of each observation period (2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017). Firms without BvD ID code (the firm's unique identification code used by Orbis) and with missing information on turnover have been removed from this initial selection.

In order to apply the employee threshold (i.e. number of employees between 50 and 4999), we considered the number of employees at the beginning of each observation period. As information on the number of employees is missing for about 40% of firms in Orbis, we use imputed data in case the actual number of employees was missing. We obtained the predicted value of the number of employees on the basis of firm's turnover, age, industry-, country- and year-fixed effects.

Eventually, after predicting the missing values for the number of employees we applied the number of employee's threshold to identify the European medium-sized firms at the beginning of each growth period (Table 1).

Table 1. European medium-sized firms

Year	N. of medium-sized firms
2008	234,990
2009	249,661
2010	257,689
2011	283,749
2012	301,876
2013	317,166
2014	328,210
2015	426,450
2016	399,847
2017	404,009

2.2.2 Selection of fast growing firms

We applied the definition of fast growing firms developed by OECD to select European medium-sized firms that experienced fast growth rates in the periods 2008-11, 2009-12, 2010-13, 2011-14, 2012-15, 2013-16, 2014-17, 2015-18, 2016-19 and 2017-20.

According to the OECD definition, firms with average annualized growth of greater than 20% over a three-year period, should be considered as high-growth firms. Growth is measured by either the number of employees or by turnover.

Following the above definition, we identified FGMFs using both employment and turnover growth thresholds for each of the periods 2008-11, 2009-12, 2010-13, 2011-14, 2012-15, 2013-16, 2014-17, 2015-18, 2016-19 and 2017-20 (Table 2).

Table 2. European FGMFs

Growth Period	N. of FGMFs
2008-11	15,424
2009-12	21,847
2010-13	14,936
2011-14	21,218
2012-15	21,273
2013-16	22,732
2014-17	24,521
2015-18	27,271
2016-19	29,872
2017-20	23,037

It is worth noting that the sum of FGMFs in the seven cohorts reported in Table 2 is higher than the number of FGMFs in the Cheetah dataset (129,752). This is because some FGMFs have experienced fast growth in more than one observation period.

2.2.3 Data collection and organization of accounting information

For the sample of FGMFs we downloaded from Orbis accounting information (balance sheet, income statement and cash-flow) for the period 2007-2021.

For firms that were included in the prior version of the Cheetah dataset (FGMFs in the cohorts 2008-11, 2009-12, 2010-13, 2011-14, 2012-15, 2013-16 and 2014-17), we updated the accounting information (originally available for the period 2007-17) to add new accounting data for the years 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021.

For the three cohorts of FGMFs added with the version 3.0 of Cheetah (2015-18, 2016-19 and 2017-20) we downloaded from Orbis accounting information for the entire period 2007-2021.

We also double checked the consistency of accounting information for FGMFs in the prior version of the Cheetah dataset with the more updated information available in Orbis (as in 2022). This allowed to identify a small number of duplicates and inconsistencies that lead to the elimination of a small fraction (around 1%) of FGMFs originally included in the prior of the Cheetah dataset.

Accounting information of FGMFs is available in the Main Table of the Cheetah dataset.

2.2.4 Data collection and organization of ownership information

Information on the ownership structure of FGMFs has been obtained using the Orbis Ownership sub-database, which contains information on a firm's equity ownership structure, specifically:

- names of the shareholders;
- ownership shares (direct or total);
- type of shareholder (corporate, individuals, State...);
- country and industry of operation of the shareholder.

Based on the direct ownership shares and the type of shareholder we checked whether a FGMF was independent in each year during the period 2007-18. A FGMF is considered independent in each year if:

- the sum of the shares of individual shareholders is greater than 50%;
- in case the sum of shares of individual shareholders is lower than 50%, the highest share of other shareholders must be lower than 25%.

Information on direct ownership shares, type, country and industry of operation of shareholders, and on the independency status of FGMFs is available in the Ownership Table of the Cheetah dataset. The Ownership Table contains information on 606,627 shareholder-FGMF dyads.

2.2.5 Data collection and organization of information on M&A activity

Information on M&A activity of FGMFs has been retrieved from Zephyr (<https://zephyr.bvdinfo.com>).

For each FGMFs we downloaded information on (completed or completed assumed) M&A deals occurred in the period 2007-21 that involved the focal FGMF as acquirer.

We then downloaded information on the deal structure (e.g. deal value, announced and completed dates, acquired stakes) and on the characteristics of the target (i.e. acquired) firms (e.g. name, country and industry of operation).

Information on M&A activity of FGMFs is available in the M&A Table of the Cheetah dataset. The M&A Table contains information on 30,554 FGMF-target firm-date triads.

2.2.6 Geocoding

We downloaded from Orbis the complete addressed for all FGMFs. These firms have been then geocoded using the RISIS CorTexT service to retrieve latitude and longitude coordinates.

Specifically, we use the city and the country to retrieve from CorTexT the latitudes and longitudes of each firm. We manually checked the addresses for which CorTexT returned a confidence less than 1, and we manually repaired them by looking up the focal firm's address on Google Maps. We also put in place additional checks on the country, the location and the label returned by CorTexT. We also manually check all the addresses for which CorTexT did not locate at the "locality" level. In particular, we set the geolocation to missing for the addresses that CorTexT located only at the country level, instead of at the required city level.

On the basis of the geographical coordinates, we associated information on NUTS regions.

Geographical information of FGMFs is available in the Main Table of the Cheetah dataset.

2.3 Information on variables

Table 3, Table 4 and Table 5 describe variables names and descriptions.

Table 3. Description of variables in the Cheetah dataset – Main Table

Variable name	Variable description
id	Firm identification code.
firmreg_id	FirmReg identification code.
bvd_id	BvD ID (Orbis).
name	Firm name.
previous_name	Previous firm name.
country_code	Country ISO code.
country	Country.
city	City.
address	Address.
latitude	Latitude.
longitude	Longitude.
nuts3_code	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics – level 3 code.
nuts2_code	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics – level 2 code.
nuts1_code	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics – level 1 code.
foundation	Foundation year.
nace_core	NACE Rev. 2 core code (4 digits).
cohortYEAR	Dummy=1 if the firm is medium-sized at the beginning of the period (midsizedYEAR=1) and fast growing (FG_employee_samplePERIOD=1 OR FG_turnover_samplePERIOD=1). Year: 2008-2017.
sum_cohort	Number of periods a FGMF is fast growing.
midsizedYEAR	Dummy=1 if the firm is medium-sized. Year: 2008-2017.
FG_employee_samplePERIOD	Dummy=1 if the firm is fast growing (employees). Period: 2008-11, 2009-12, 2010-13, 2011-14, 2012-15, 2013-16, 2014-17, 2015-18, 2016-19, 2017-20.
FG_turnover_samplePERIOD	Dummy=1 if the firm is fast growing (turnover). Period: 2008-11, 2009-12, 2010-13, 2011-14, 2012-15, 2013-16, 2014-17, 2015-18, 2016-19, 2017-20.
FG_employeePERIOD	Average annualized growth rate based on employees. Period: 2008-11, 2009-12, 2010-13, 2011-14, 2012-15, 2013-16, 2014-17, 2015-18, 2016-19, 2017-20.
FG_turnoverPERIOD	Average annualized growth rate based on turnover. Period: 2008-11, 2009-12, 2010-13, 2011-14, 2012-15, 2013-16, 2014-17, 2015-18, 2016-19, 2017-20.
turnoverYEAR	Operating revenue (Turnover) th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
tot_assetYEAR	Total assets th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
num_empYEAR	Number of employees. Year: 2007-2020.
cost_empYEAR	Costs of employees th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
salesYEAR	Sales th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
added_valueYEAR	Added value th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
ebitdaYEAR	EBITDA th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
ebitYEAR	Operating P/L [=EBIT] th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
depreciationYEAR	Depreciation & Amortization th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
net_incomeYEAR	P/L for period [=Net income] th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
cashflowYEAR	Cash flow th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
cash_equivalentYEAR	Cash & cash equivalent th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
intang_assetYEAR	Intangible fixed assets th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
tang_assetYEAR	Tangible fixed assets th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
fix_assetYEAR	Fixed Assets th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
other_fix_assetYEAR	Other fixed assets th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
current_assetYEAR	Current assets th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
other_current_assetYEAR	Other current assets th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
working_capYEAR	Working capital th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
longterm_debtYEAR	Long term debt th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
current_liabYEAR	Current liabilities th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
tot_equityYEAR	Shareholders funds th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
interest_expensesYEAR	Interest paid th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.
income_before_taxYEAR	P/L before tax th EUR. Year: 2007-2020.

Table 4. Description of variables in the Cheetah dataset – Ownership Table

Variable name	Variable description
id	Firm identification code.
s_name	Shareholder name
s_bvd	Shareholder BvD ID - Feb. 2020
s_country_code	Shareholder country ISO code
s_nace_core	Shareholder NACE Rev. 2 core code (4 digits)
s_type	Shareholder type
s_type_detailed	Shareholder type (detail)
s_YEAR	Shareholder direct ownership stake. Year: 2007-2018
main_s_YEAR	Dummy=1 if the shareholder has the highest direct ownership stake. Year: 2007-2018.
indepinyear_YEAR	Dummy=1 if the firm is independent (not controlled) based on direct ownership. Year: 2007-2018.

Table 5. Description of variables in the Cheetah dataset – M&A Table

Variable name	Variable description
id	Firm identification code.
deal_number	Zephyr deal number.
t_bvd	Target BvD ID number.
t_name	Target name.
t_country_code	Target country ISO code.
t_nacecore	Target NACE Rev. 2 core code (4 digits).
deal_type	Deal type.
deal_status	Deal status.
announced_date	Announced date.
completed_date	Completed date.
announced_year	Announced year.
completed_year	Completed year.
deal_value	Deal value th EUR.
initial_stake	Initial stake (%).
acquired_stake	Acquired stake (%).
final_stake	Final stake (%).
deal_headline	Deal headline.
deal_comments	Deal comments.

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

Sectorial classification follows the NACE Rev. 2 classification. Table 6 shows the number of FGMFs according to the NACE Division (2-digit NACE code).

Table 6. Sectoral coverage – NACE Division

NACE code	NACE description	N.	%
01	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	1,323	1.0
02	Forestry and logging	165	0.1
03	Fishing and aquaculture	145	0.1
05	Mining of coal and lignite	30	0.0
06	Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas	172	0.1
07	Mining of metal ores	60	0.1
08	Other mining and quarrying	291	0.2
09	Mining support service activities	324	0.3
10	Manufacture of food products	3,195	2.5
11	Manufacture of beverages	282	0.2
12	Manufacture of tobacco products	39	0.0
13	Manufacture of textiles	632	0.5
14	Manufacture of wearing apparel	1,037	0.8
15	Manufacture of leather and related products	537	0.4
16	Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture...	763	0.6

NACE code	NACE description	N.	%
17	Manufacture of paper and paper products	545	0.4
18	Printing and reproduction of recorded media	407	0.3
19	Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products	99	0.1
20	Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products	1,159	0.9
21	Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	604	0.5
22	Manufacture of rubber and plastic products	1,558	1.2
23	Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	1,001	0.8
24	Manufacture of basic metals	898	0.7
25	Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	3,644	2.8
26	Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products	1,423	1.1
27	Manufacture of electrical equipment	1,179	0.9
28	Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c.	2,852	2.2
29	Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	1,330	1.0
30	Manufacture of other transport equipment	672	0.5
31	Manufacture of furniture	809	0.6
32	Other manufacturing	897	0.7
33	Repair and installation of machinery and equipment	1,012	0.8
35	Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	2,257	1.7
36	Water collection, treatment and supply	179	0.1
37	Sewerage	77	0.1
38	Waste collection, treatment and disposal activities; materials recovery	1,114	0.9
39	Remediation activities and other waste management services	95	0.1
41	Construction of buildings	4,350	3.4
42	Civil engineering	2,276	1.8
43	Specialised construction activities	3,394	2.6
45	Wholesale and retail trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	2,239	1.7
46	Wholesale trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	7,394	5.7
47	Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	4,645	3.6
49	Land transport and transport via pipelines	3,078	2.4
50	Water transport	253	0.2
51	Air transport	165	0.1
52	Warehousing and support activities for transportation	2,782	2.1
53	Postal and courier activities	247	0.2
55	Accommodation	1,893	1.5
56	Food and beverage service activities	2,169	1.7
58	Publishing activities	718	0.6
59	Motion picture, video and television programme production, sound recording and music...	688	0.5
60	Programming and broadcasting activities	170	0.1
61	Telecommunications	669	0.5
62	Computer programming, consultancy and related activities	4,097	3.2
63	Information service activities	656	0.5
64	Financial service activities, except insurance and pension funding	8,358	6.4
65	Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding, except compulsory social security	789	0.6
66	Activities auxiliary to financial services and insurance activities	1,449	1.1
68	Real estate activities	2,804	2.2
69	Legal and accounting activities	723	0.6
70	Activities of head offices; management consultancy activities	4,008	3.1
71	Architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis	2,026	1.6
72	Scientific research and development	710	0.6
73	Advertising and market research	971	0.8
74	Other professional, scientific and technical activities	832	0.6
75	Veterinary activities	43	0.0
77	Rental and leasing activities	838	0.7
78	Employment activities	3,654	2.8
79	Travel agency, tour operator and other reservation service and related activities	600	0.5
80	Security and investigation activities	1,600	1.2
81	Services to buildings and landscape activities	2,719	2.1
82	Office administrative, office support and other business support activities	3,770	2.9
84	Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	766	0.6

NACE code	NACE description	N.	%
85	Education	3,444	2.7
86	Human health activities	2,661	2.1
87	Residential care activities	1,651	1.3
88	Social work activities without accommodation	1,611	1.2
90	Creative, arts and entertainment activities	380	0.3
91	Libraries, archives, museums and other cultural activities	207	0.2
92	Gambling and betting activities	534	0.4
93	Sports activities and amusement and recreation activities	1,149	0.9
94	Activities of membership organisations	1,178	0.9
95	Repair of computers and personal and household goods	128	0.1
96	Other personal service activities	957	0.7
97	Activities of households as employers of domestic personnel	2	0.0
98	Undifferentiated goods-and services-producing activities of private households for own use	5	0.0
99	Activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies	19	0.0
NA	Missing NACE information	4,477	3.4

Overall, FGMFs are relatively young. The median foundation year of is 2001. Table 7 shows the distribution of FGMFs by foundation period. Around 80% of FGMFs have been incorporated from 1990 onwards.

Table 6. Temporal coverage – Foundation period

Foundation period	N.	%
Before 1980	14,359	11.1
1980-1989	10,947	8.4
1990-1999	32,736	25.2
2000-2009	43,521	33.5
After 2009	27,793	21.4
NA	396	0.3

As to the geographical coverage, the Cheetah dataset includes information on the country, NUTS region and exact geographical coordinates (i.e. latitude and longitude). Table 7 shows the distribution of FGMFs by country.

Table 7. Geographical coverage – Country

Country	N.	%
Austria	1,665	1.3
Belgium	1,937	1.5
Bulgaria	4,717	3.7
Croatia	986	0.8
Cyprus	122	0.1
Czech Republic	6,527	5.1
Denmark	641	0.5
Estonia	598	0.5
Finland	1,849	1.4
France	7,915	6.1
Germany	10,601	8.2
Greece	1,177	0.9
Hungary	3,516	2.7
Ireland	1,893	1.5
Italy	13,890	10.8
Latvia	1,051	0.8
Lithuania	1,997	1.6
Luxembourg	501	0.4
Malta	606	0.5
Netherlands	3,496	2.7
Norway	2,221	1.7
Poland	13,951	10.8

Country	N.	%
Portugal	2,960	2.3
Romania	6,113	4.7
Slovakia	430	0.5
Slovenia	8,652	0.3
Spain	3,003	6.7
Sweden	2,542	2.3
Switzerland	684	2.0
United Kingdom	22,779	17.7

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

Table 8, Table 9 and Table 10 report the number of missing values and their percentages with respect to the total number of observations for some key variables included in the Cheetah dataset.

Table 8. Missing information – Main Table

Variable	N. missing	Total obs.	% missing
id	0	129,752	0.0
country_code	725	129,752	0.6
city	886	129,752	0.7
foundation	396	129,752	0.3
nace_core	4,477	129,752	3.5
turnover07	68,811	92,755	74.2
turnover12	18,455	114,465	16.1
turnover17	19,636	129,208	15.2
turnover21	38,164	129,752	29.4
tot_asset07	75,226	92,755	81.1
tot_asset12	19,357	114,465	16.9
tot_asset17	19,931	129,208	15.4
tot_asset21	33,302	129,752	25.7
num_emp07	71,144	92,755	76.7
num_emp12	37,527	114,465	32.8
num_emp17	29,687	129,208	23.0
num_emp21	43,616	129,752	33.6
ebit07	75,554	92,755	81.5
ebit12	26,604	114,465	23.2
ebit17	25,614	129,208	19.8
ebit 21	38,369	129,752	29.6

Table 9. Missing information – Ownership Table

Variable	N. missing	Total obs.	% missing
id	0	606,627	0.0
s_name	14,331	606,627	2.4
s_country_code	129,560	606,627	21.4
s_nace_core	67,109	606,627	11.1
s_type	14,331	606,627	2.4

Table 10. Missing information – M&A Table

Variable	N. missing	Total obs.	% missing
id	0	30,554	0.0
t_name	354	30,554	1.2
t_country_code	614	30,554	2.0
t_nacecore	378	30,554	1.2
deal_type	0	30,554	0.0
announced_year	0	30,554	0.0
completed_year	5,739	30,554	18.8
deal_value	22,080	30,554	72.3
acquired_stake	3,295	30,554	10.8%

3 Technical specifications

3.1 Information on the data base system

The database is currently available in .csv and STATA (.dta) format.

3.2 Technical variable definition

The database is organized in three tables (Main, Ownership, and M&A). Table 11, Table 12 and Table 13 report names and types of variables in Cheetah. The unique identifier is reported in bold.

Table 11. Variable types – Main Table

Variable name	Variable type
id	String
firmreg_id	String
bvd_id	String
name	String
previous_name	String
country_code	String
country	String
city	String
address	String
latitude	Float
longitude	Float
nuts3_code	String
nuts2_code	String
nuts1_code	String
foundation	Integer
nace_core	String
cohortYEAR	Boolean
sum_cohort	Integer
midsizedYEAR	Boolean
FG_employee_samplePERIOD	Boolean
FG_turnover_samplePERIOD	Boolean
FG_employeePERIOD	Float
FG_turnoverPERIOD	Float
turnoverYEAR	Float
tot_assetYEAR	Float
num_empYEAR	Float
cost_empYEAR	Float
salesYEAR	Float
added_valueYEAR	Float
ebitdaYEAR	Float
ebitYEAR	Float
depreciationYEAR	Float
net_incomeYEAR	Float
cashflowYEAR	Float
cash_equivalentYEAR	Float
intang_assetYEAR	Float
tang_assetYEAR	Float
fix_assetYEAR	Float
other_fix_assetYEAR	Float
current_assetYEAR	Float
other_current_assetYEAR	Float
working_capYEAR	Float
longterm_debtYEAR	Float
current_liabYEAR	Float
tot_equityYEAR	Float

Variable name	Variable type
interest_expensesYEAR	Float
income_before_taxYEAR	Float

Table 12. Description of variables in the Cheetah dataset – Ownership Table

Variable name	Variable type
id	String
s_name	String
s_bvd	String
s_country_code	String
s_nace_core	String
s_type	String
s_type_detailed	String
s_YEAR	Float
main_s_YEAR	Boolean
indepinyear_YEAR	Boolean

Table 13. Description of variables in the Cheetah dataset – M&A Table

Variable name	Variable type
id	String
deal_number	String
t_bvd	String
t_name	String
t_country_code	String
t_nacecore	String
deal_type	String
deal_status	String
announced_date	Date
completed_date	Date
announced_year	Integer
completed_year	Integer
deal_value	Float
initial_stake	Float
acquired_stake	Float
final_stake	Float
deal_headline	String
deal_comments	String

3.3 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures (if applicable)

The Cheetah dataset is integrated with the other firm-level RISIS databases through the FirmReg facility. FirmReg is a central facility within RISIS, which aims at uniquely identifying and tracking over time the businesses included in RISIS. For each entity, Cheetah is connected to FirmReg with an unambiguous and stable (over time) identifier.

At the geographical level, Cheetah is harmonized with the other research infrastructures in RISIS by adopting the NUTS classification of administrative units (as provided by Eurostat).

Integration of Cheetah in the RCF is allowed with anonymised firm names, which is essential for legal issues due to data retrieval from commercial databases. Only in specific cases when a high level of data protection is guaranteed, such as in case of physical visits and direct research collaborations with the datasets' owners, firms' names may be disclosed.

4 Scientific use cases and main references

In recent years, fast/high growth firms received considerable attention by academic scholars and policymakers (Coad et al., 2014). One of the reasons for this increased interest is the fact that these firms play a crucial role in creating new jobs and employment.

The academic literature on high growth/fast growing firms has pointed out that firm performance appears to be highly skewed and most firms do not experience fast/high growth (Stanley et al., 1996; Bottazzi and Secchi, 2006), that growth is difficult to foresee (Marsili, 2001; Coad, 2009), and that growth tends not to persist over time (Coad, 2007; Daunfeldt and Halvarsson, 2012). In addition, this literature has analysed the characteristics of high growth/fast growing firms, in terms of: size (Delmar and Davidsson, 1998; Delmar et al., 2003), age (Delmar et al., 2003; Haltiwanger et al., 2013), sector (Delmar et al., 2003; Davidsson and Delmar, 2003, 2006), or country (Schreyer, 2000; Bravo-Biosca, 2010).

Despite the increasing interest on fast growing firms, one category of firms received somewhat less attention: medium-sized firms. Most studies, in fact, tend to focus on either small entrepreneurial fast growing firms or large ones.

The Cheetah dataset offers the unique opportunity to address this research gap, providing original data about a large sample of FGMFs. For instance, the role of FGMFs within the local ecosystems could be analysed thanks to the large geographical coverage of the dataset (EU27, UK, Norway and Switzerland), while the sectorial classification of FGMFs could be explored more in depth in order to find different growth patterns (understanding if countries tend to specialize within particular sectors). Furthermore, the panel data structure of the dataset (regarding the financial data) could be exploited to investigate the determinants of growth persistence over time.

Please refer to the RISIS policy brief based on Cheetah for some examples of policy recommendations that can be derived from the Cheetah dataset (Camerani and Guerini, 2019). Also, Moretti et al. (2023) provide evidence on the process and strategies of growth FGMFs.

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